

THE INFLUENCE OF HISTORICAL ASPECTS ON THE LANGUAGE OF ADVERTISING

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ABSTRACT. This paper aims to investigate the impact of historical contexts on shaping the language and discourse used in advertising. By delving into distinct historical epochs and their intricate ties to specific linguistic techniques, this research unfurls the multifaceted manner in which shifts in culture, society, and economics have woven the intricate tapestry of advertising language. The study meticulously employs a nuanced analytical approach, drawing upon a diverse array of examples spanning across epochs and eras. It not only sheds light on the dynamic evolution and adaptation of advertising language over the ages but also accentuates its profound interconnectedness with the broader narratives of history. Through this comprehensive lens, the study unveils the inseparable bond between the language of advertising and the sweeping currents of history. It becomes evident how advertising language serves as a reflection of, and a responsive force to, the ever-evolving societal norms, cultural dynamics, and economic paradigms, encapsulating the essence of centuries-long historical changes.

KEYWORDS: historical contexts, advertising language, linguistic techniques, culture, society, economics, evolution, societal norms.

The language embedded within advertising operates as a potent lens, offering a vivid portrayal through which historical influences are vividly brought to the forefront. Spanning epochs, advertising stands not merely as a passive reflection but as an active catalyst, playing a pivotal role in mirroring societal transformations while concurrently instigating profound cultural shifts. The core objective of this study is to meticulously unravel the intricate interplay between historical undercurrents and the language encapsulated within advertising. This exploration also aims to dissect how diverse

epochs have intricately woven the fabric of advertising discourse, shaping and reshaping its contours in response to the dynamic currents of history.

Coca-Cola`s enduring Christmas campaigns, spanning the 1930s, exemplify the profound impact of historical influence on advertising language. By prominently featuring Santa Claus in their ads, Coca-Cola adeptly taps into the rich historical imagery linked with the festive season (Pendergrast, 2013). The language employed within these campaigns strategically aims to evoke a sense of nostalgia, drawing upon deeply rooted cultural and historical traditions. Through this deliberate utilization of historical iconography and language, Coca-Cola creates an emotional connection with consumers, fostering a resonance that extends beyond mere product promotion to embodying the spirit of the holiday season, thereby solidifying its place in the collective holiday traditions and memories of audiences worldwide.

The slogan «*Open Happiness*» **was** introduced in 2009 and aimed to evoke positive emotions associated with the brand. It was used in various advertising campaigns featuring people enjoying Coca-Cola and the happiness it brings. It focuses on the idea that Coca-Cola is not just a beverage but a source of joy and positivity. Furthermore, it encourages consumers to associate the act of opening a Coca-Cola with the experience of happiness and delight. The slogan «*Taste the Feeling*» was launched in 2016 and emphasized the sensory experience of drinking Coca-Cola. The slogan was used across multiple platforms, portraying people enjoying Coca-Cola in everyday moments. It suggests that consuming Coca-Cola is not just about the taste but also about the emotions and experiences it evokes, aiming to create a personal and emotional connection with the consumers. «*It's the Real Thing*» was introduced in the 1960s and became a classic tagline for Coca-Cola. It was featured in commercials and print advertisements, reinforcing Coca-Cola's authenticity and quality. This slogan presented Coca-Cola as the authentic, original cola beverage, distinguishing it from imitators or substitutes. It aimed to solidify Coca-Cola's identity and legacy, emphasizing its unique taste and heritage in the soft drink market.

These slogans effectively capture different aspects of Coca-Cola's branding strategy, aiming to evoke motions, emphasize sensory experiences, and assert the brand's authenticity and uniqueness in the market.

Historical Context and Linguistic Strategies.

Historical epochs wield a substantial influence over the language utilized in advertising, intricately molding linguistic strategies to align with the dominant societal norms of their time. An illustrative example of this phenomenon lies within the era of the Industrial Revolution, where advertising tactics underwent a noticeable transformation. Advertisements during this period adopted an elaborate and verbose language, often incorporating meticulous and detailed descriptions to underscore the uniqueness and innovation of products. This linguistic approach catered specifically to an audience transitioning from agrarian-based livelihoods to a burgeoning industrial lifestyle. As noted by Berger (2014), this shift in advertising language served as a strategic response to societal changes, capturing the attention of a populace embracing the novel advancements of the industrial era.

Additionally, periods of wartime have significantly shaped and imprinted enduring characteristics on the language employed in advertising. The propaganda campaigns witnessed during World War I and II stand out as pivotal examples in this regard. These wartime initiatives introduced persuasive communication tactics infused with emotive language, strategically designed to evoke profound sentiments of patriotism and collective unity among the populace. Notably, slogans like «*Buy War Bonds*» exemplify this approach, skillfully appealing to consumers' innate sense of duty, loyalty, and communal solidarity (Cook, 2001). Such advertising endeavors not only aimed to mobilize financial support for the war efforts but also deeply ingrained in the public consciousness a profound sense of national obligation and unity, utilizing language as a potent tool to evoke powerful emotions and align public sentiment with national objectives.

The slogan «*Keep Calm and Carry On*» was used in British propaganda posters to instill resilience and determination in the face of adversity. These campaigns

demonstrate how historical context can shape the language of advertising to align with the dominant sentiments and objectives of a particular time period.

The influential «1984» Apple commercial aired during the Super Bowl stands as a testament to the power of historical events in advertising. This iconic ad ingeniously drew inspiration from George Orwell's seminal novel, utilizing the historical context of a dystopian society to position Apple as the harbinger of liberation from societal conformity. By deftly incorporating historical references and evocative language, Apple strategically implied that its product represented a paradigm shift, symbolizing a revolutionary break from the chains of uniformity (Stefan Toeple, 2002). This groundbreaking advertisement exemplifies how historical contexts can be masterfully interwoven into advertising language to craft a narrative that resonates deeply with audiences, invoking emotions and associations linked to historical events for impactful messaging.

Evolution of Advertising Language.

The evolution of advertising language distinctly showcases its capacity to adapt in response to shifts in society and advancements in technology. Particularly notable is its transformative response to the emergence of television and radio as influential mediums. During this era, advertising underwent a significant transition, embracing succinct, memorable slogans and catchy jingles that aimed to captivate the attention of audiences inundated with these new forms of media. An illustrative glimpse into this shift lies within the 1950s, marked by the ascent of memorable slogans like «*I Like Ike*» in political advertising and «*A Diamond is Forever*» in diamond marketing. These slogans not only exemplified concise messaging but also reflected and reinforced prevalent cultural values and societal aspirations at the time (Leiss, 2017). The deliberate use of these slogans underscores the adaptability of advertising language, demonstrating its agility in encapsulating and promoting the prevailing ideals and desires of a society navigating through an era of technological innovation and shifting cultural paradigms.

Moreover, the advent of globalization and the ushering in of the digital age have sparked a revolutionary transformation in advertising language, marking a pivotal shift

towards the integration and fusion of diverse linguistic elements. Present-day advertising has evolved to encompass a rich tapestry of multicultural and multilingual facets, strategically tailored to resonate with and appeal to diverse global markets. This adaptation involves the deliberate incorporation of varied languages, cultural symbols, and nuances to effectively communicate with an increasingly interconnected global audience. Leveraging the expansive reach of social media platforms and the influence wielded by digital personalities, contemporary advertising strategies pivotally engage with a digitally connected audience. By harnessing the power of these platforms and collaborating with influential figures, brands tactically navigate the intricate landscape of the digital realm, fostering deeper connections and resonating more authentically with the diverse sensibilities and preferences of their global consumer base.

Consequently, the language employed in advertising acts as a multifaceted mirror that reflects the intricate tapestry of historical contexts, dynamically adapting and evolving in tandem with societal, cultural, and technological transformations. This adaptive nature underscores its profound responsiveness to the ever-changing landscape, encapsulating the zeitgeist of each epoch it traverses. Grasping the nuances of historical influences on advertising language unveils invaluable insights into the evolutionary trajectory of communication strategies spanning different eras. Delving deeper into this relationship unveils a treasure trove of understanding regarding not just the shifts in advertising techniques, but also offers profound insights into the nuances of consumer behavior, the complex interplay of cultural dynamics, and the trajectory of communication trends that shape the fabric of modern society. Further research into the symbiotic relationship between historical aspects and the language of advertising promises to unravel deeper layers of understanding, shedding light on the intricate mechanisms that underpin consumer choices, cultural evolution, and the ever-evolving dynamics of communication in contemporary society.

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